

SECTION 377: AN UNNATURAL OFFENCE?

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ABSTRACT

The world's LGBT situations are not the same anywhere. It is extremely tough to live as an LGBT person in various regions of the world. Homosexuality is prohibited in many nations and is punished by jail or death. Transgender persons are denied fundamental human rights and protections in several nations. The world's lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) circumstances vary greatly depending on where you reside. For example, it is quite difficult to live as an LGBT person in certain areas of the world, although it is much easy in others.

We have a general understanding of the LGBT people and their circumstances, but there are more topics we should discuss. You may think of us as an Indian society that is accepting it and becoming intelligent. We will go over the good and bad aspects of this minor sexuality in greater depth. Yes, we implemented some societal improvements. Changing anything is assumed to be simple, but when we do it, we encounter a slew of complications, and it is a resounding yes that there is plenty to reconstruct, investigate, and fix.

Life isn't simple if you're L, G, B, T, or Q. Half of society doesn't get you, and the other half is terrified of you. Religious extremists will speak about your misdeeds and target the worst aspects of your identity. Your partner's employment may be threatened simply because they wish to marry someone like you. You are frequently denied vital services that many people take for granted, such as a proper night in a hotel, access to public housing, or legal safeguards against workplace discrimination.

Many LGBT supporters have devoted efforts to seeking answers to the challenges these adolescents confront to address the melancholy and anxiety

that these youth experience. Gay-Straight Alliances (GSAs) may help LGBT children feel less anxious, according to prior research. However, because these groups are still relatively young and few, there is little research on LGBT youth organizations. This research makes a first attempt to evaluate the benefits that these bigger organizations provide for LGBT kids. 17 members of an urban LGBT center in the Midwest were questioned using a qualitative, semi-structured procedure about four main topics: social support, good peer interaction, positive adult role models, and safe places. The results show that all four regions were helpful in lowering anxiety and empower members similar to what research shows for GSAs. Results from this exploration offer insights into the potential for large youth organizations to positively impact LGBT youth.

INTRODUCTION

Society's viewpoints on the LGBT community have shifted dramatically over the last two decades. With progress, however, come new terms and titles for all of those who identify more different than heterosexual and cisgender.

We must realize our full potential in the modern world when society, the media, and the educational system are all more inclusive. To do this, we must discuss both the numerous successes that have been achieved as well as the hardships that our community has faced. The LGBTQIA+ community has come a long way, but there are still many obstacles to overcome. There are 37 websites and applications that will instruct you on some of the subjects that are most frequently discussed in our community, such as how to utilize kyriarchy effectively and why it matters.

We are trying our best to liberalize and positively change our society. But can we still see changes around? Maybe yes but not steady. Talking about the

LGBT community in our society has always been difficult to date. So basically protecting their rights is not only the motto but to giving the same priority to this section of the people.

Today, homosexuality and queer identities may be acceptable to more Indian youths than ever before, but within the boundaries of family, home, and school, acceptance of their sexuality and freedom to openly express their gender choices remain a constant struggle for LGBT.

AN UNNATURAL OFFENCE?

Our constitution addresses it as an unnatural offense in section 377 but practically this is not applicable, this is natural as it's actually what an individual comes up with and gets to know about his/herself which is completely normal and is supposed to be considered and to be acceptable. This realization naturally occurs without any individual's fault.

The Supreme Court of India has finally overturned this legislation, stating that it violates constitutional rights and is not valid anymore. The verdict has been welcomed by LGBTQIA+ activists who have been campaigning for this change for years.

DO THEY HAVE EQUAL OPPORTUNITIES?

In a culture where adoption and surrogacy are widespread, many rights are granted to those involved, yet we forbid homosexual couples from using surrogacy to have children in favor of adoption. All people have a profound

desire to be their children's genetic parents, but owing to laws and norms, this is not feasible.

We are in a new age of life, but We document and expose abuses based on sexual orientation and gender identity throughout the world, including torture, murder and executions, arrests under unjust laws, unequal treatment, censorship, medical abuses, discrimination in health and jobs and housing, domestic violence, abuses against children, and denial of family rights and recognition. We advocate for laws and policies that will protect everyone's dignity. We work for a world where all people can enjoy their rights fully.

CONTEXT

Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transsexual/transgender, and queer/questioning (LGBTQ) people are a minority and neglected population with distinct and sometimes unidentified health needs. The LGBTQ population suffers healthcare challenges such as trouble accessing health insurance and stigmatization by some healthcare practitioners based on sexual orientation or gender identity. Furthermore, as compared to heterosexual and gender-aligned populations, the LGBTQ community faces higher cancer risks due to lower detection rates, less utilization of routine health care, and a higher incidence of cancer risk factors. According to recent research by Quinn et al.; anal, breast, cervical, colorectal, endometrial, lung, and prostate cancers may impact the LGBTQ community disproportionately. The goal of this investigation was to identify the attitudes, knowledge, and practice habits of healthcare clinicians who specialize in these seven forms of cancer.

The LGBT community is a group that has been historically discriminated against and marginalized. Despite the progress made in recent years, there are

still many opportunities for the LGBT community to be more included in all aspects of society.

1. In the workplace

- Provide an inclusive work environment for LGBT employees.
- Be mindful of gender identity and sexual orientation when hiring new employees.
- Promote equal benefits and treatment to all employees regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity.

2. In education

- Include LGBTQ history in the school curriculum.
- Offer scholarships to LGBTQ students.
- Support LGBTQ clubs, organizations, and events on campus.

3. In healthcare

Provide transgender surgery as a covered service under health insurance policies.

SURVEY

The poll comprised 1,528 self-identified LGBTQ persons aged 18 and up who were recruited and administered using NORC's (National Opinion Research Centre) American Speak online panel between June 9 and June 30, 2020. Given

the size of the total sample, CAP (Competency Assessment Programme) was able to isolate results that were relevant to major community subgroups such as race, age, education, income, handicap, gender, or gender identity. The entire study results, as well as a thorough summary of the methodology, are on file with the authors. Overall, this survey indicates that many LGBTQ persons continue to encounter discrimination in their personal lives, workplaces, and public spaces, as well as in their access to crucial health care. This prejudice has numerous negative effects on their financial, mental, and physical well-being. Many LGBTQ persons indicate that they have changed their life to escape prejudice and the emotional pain that comes with unequal treatment. Younger generations report higher levels of discrimination and related issues than older generations, and problems linked with discrimination are particularly prominent among transgender people, people of color, and people with disabilities. Anxiety over the corona virus adds another layer of worry to this group, particularly among those who are most vulnerable in terms of their health or front-line work status.

POSITIVE ATTRIBUTE

We are aware of the possibility that senior attorney Saurabh Kripal would be India's first homosexual judge. After four years of deliberation, the Supreme Court collegiums have finally approved his appointment as a judge of the Delhi High Court. It's a common legal claim that the delay in recommending his name was due to his sexual orientation. If he is chosen, his appointment will signal a watershed moment in LGBT rights. This means that everyone may achieve anything he or she desires, improve his or her level of living, and lead and live life responsibly and with dignity without hesitation or pressure.

IRONY OF THE SOCIETY

Lesbians in other regions of the country are subjected to family-sanctioned corrective rapes, which are frequently carried out by family members. Vyjayanti Vasanta Mogli, a transwoman LGBT activist and public policy scholar at Tata Institute of Social Sciences in Hyderabad who has openly discussed her abuse at school, claims that lesbians and transmen in rural areas are at the bottom of the hierarchy when it comes to basic human rights within the family and village unit.

When discussing the rural socioeconomic milieu, she quotes B.R. Ambedkar. "Ambedkar saw the village as a unit of violence, and this is especially true for LGBT problems". She says "Village doctors and babas sometimes advise rape to cure lesbians of homosexuality." Refusing to marry results in further physical assault. Stories of family acceptance that you see on TV and in other media are more of an urban occurrence."

Every year, suicides by lesbians make news in educated urban India. It's no surprise, however, that a panel recently determined that the main risk facing lesbians in India is from their own families.

In India, the majority of people have a negative view of LGBTQ individuals. This is owing to the ancient beliefs and customs of Indian culture, which are still strongly ingrained in the nation. We are more inclined to select a society where people are connected by love, equality, and respect, yet in the same society, many individuals around us have their sexual orientation, which we cannot ignore. The irony is that we show acceptance but fail to put it into practice. If I offer a clear example of situations in India, we label a gay person a 'hijada' and they still beg on the streets for money, doing nothing new. People also refer to one other as 'hijada' while abusing each other, which is utterly

disrespectful and degrading to the person being called by that word. These things continue to demonstrate that there is much to be improved, and we must address them.

CONCLUSION

The significance of LGBTQ people in the workplace has been covered in this article. It has also demonstrated how they are at a disadvantage in terms of getting and retaining work. Finally, we addressed various strategies that employers may use to make LGBTQ workers feel more comfortable and supported at work. The LGBTQ community has made strides in society and its existence. Many people, including activists, have contributed to this development. The community has seen significant progress in the last few decades and will continue to do so via its efforts. Until and unless the government grants equal status to LGBTQIA+ individuals in India, a legitimate and fair battle for societal acceptance by LGBTQIA+ will continue.

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